

CRITICAL THINKING AS THE KEY OF MULTISIDED ANALYSIS

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Most teachers will support the view that one of the main aims of education is teaching students critical thinking. In layperson's terms, critical thinking consists of seeing both sides of an issue, being open to new evidence that disconfirms your ideas, reasoning dispassionately, demanding that claims be backed by evidence, deducing and interfering conclusions from available facts, solving problems and so forth [2]. Brown and Keeley approach this concept slightly more differently. That is, they defined critical thinking in terms of a set of qualities and abilities including: 1. awareness of a set of interrelated questions; 2. ability to ask and answer critical questions at appropriate times; 3. desire to actively use the critical questions [1].

However, nowadays arguable question arises as to whether critical thinking is an ability or a skill. It should be mentioned that terms such as “skill” and “ability” differentiate to some extent in the context that “skill” is acquired and trained, while “ability” is mostly referred as inborn. Turning back to the question matter, critical thinking can be referred both as skill and ability. For this reason, some students can succeed in critical analysis at the first attempt due to the inborn ability, while other students lacking this gift have to acknowledge background information and practice it over and over in order to achieve mastery. When it comes to the definition of critical thinking, it should be taken into account that critical thinking reflects the ability of student not only looking at the issue, but also providing causes, consequences, and certainly, solutions of the topic being discussed. This ability can also reveal student's ability of synthesis of the topic not only in one particular science but also in correlation with others. For example, if the student is given a task of critical analysis on the subject of Genetically Modified Food, the student should reflect the analysis in relation to other

fields such as psychology, science, production and/or consumption. As a result, student offering the most multisided analysis should be regarded as the most successful one.

On the other hand, a student cannot fully present the ability of critical thinking without sufficient background knowledge. For instance, if a teacher asks students to look at an issue of cyber synthesis from multiple perspectives, most students will fail to fulfill the task. This situation occurs because of the shortage of background knowledge. However, if a teacher will instruct them to analyze the topic of social communication, most of the students will succeed due to the wide range of data they possess in their mind. As a consequence, it makes no sense to try to teach critical thinking devoid of factual content.

Additionally, it is proven by educators that school attendance and even academic success do not assure a student to be an effective thinker. In addition, the ability of critical thinking can be restricted by a particular area of studies. For example, a student who has learned to thoughtfully discuss the causes of annihilation of Timur’s centralized country does not even think to question how Napoleon’s country was ruined. Consequently, we can draw a conclusion that students are able to think critically in one situation but fail in another. If the context is fully analyzed and can provide enough space for critical analysis, student will try to fulfill the instruction. However, if the context is shallow and not fully defined, students can fail the task.

All things considered, we can deem that the level of critical thinking of the student greatly depends on such factors as student’s ability, background information he/she possesses, and the deepness of the context.

In order to nurture successful students with proper critical thinking skills, it is assumed that the students should be exposed to substantial amount of practice. As we mentioned above, students who possess critical thinking as inborn ability should master it by practicing whilst attendants who lack this ability and want to learn this skill have to practice even more. If one practices logic puzzles with an effective teacher, one is likely to get better at solving logic puzzles, but substantial improvement requires a great deal of practice. Unfortunately, because critical thinking curricula include many

different types of problems, students typically will not be able to manage to practice their skill sufficiently. Subsequently, it would be up to the teacher’s choice as to centralize the teaching critical thinking according to the needs of the students.

To sum up, we should restate that critical thinking can be skill and ability which is mastered mainly by practice. Moreover, it is the ability of multisided analysis of the issue in correlation with various fields of study. Critical thinking is the key to solve problems by analyzing, valuating and comparing facts and situations as the analysis of any situation in reality. Critical thinking is one of the main tools of success for students, but knowing that they should think critically is not the same as being able to do so since the process of critical thinking requires domain knowledge and practice.

Reference

1. Brown, M.N. and Keeley, S.M., 2007. Asking the right questions: A guide to critical thinking. Pearson Prentice Hall: New Jersey.
2. Willingham, D.T., 2007. Critical Thinking: Why Is It So Hard to Teach? American Educator, American Federation of Teachers.
<https://www.readingrockets.org/article/critical-thinking-why-it-so-hard-teach>